

AN AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF CERVICAL EROSION (KARNINI YONIVYAPAD): A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

In Ayurveda, disease of the female genital tract is described under Yonivyapad. Among these, *Karnini Yonivyapad* is characterized by *yoni srava* (excessive discharge), *yonikandu* (itching), *yonivedana* (pain) and local inflammation, which closely correlates with cervical pathology.^[1] In modern it closely resembles with cervical erosion, a common gynaecological disorder, which is defined as the replacement of squamous epithelium of the ectocervix. Integrative approaches using Ayurvedic local procedures have shown promising results in symptom reduction and epithelial healing. Local therapeutic measures such as *Yoni Prakshalana* (vaginal douche) with herbal decoctions and *Yoni Pichu* (intravaginal tampon therapy) using medicated oils are described as effective interventions for cleansing, healing, and pacifying vitiated *doshas*.^[2] **Main clinical findings:** A 22-year-old unmarried female reported to *Prasuti Tantra* and *Stree Roga* OPD with complaints of persistent white discharge with vaginal itching and discomfort

for the last six months. **Diagnosis:** Per speculum examination revealed cervical erosion with thick milky discharge (*Karnini Yonivyapad*). She had previously received allopathic treatment but did not achieve satisfactory relief. She denied any history of sexual exposure, systemic

illness, or recent drug intake. **Interventions:** Treatment given was *yoni prakshalana* with *yoni pichu* and *pushyanug churna* orally. **Outcome:** The therapy effectively reduced vaginal discharge, itching and local discomfort while promoting cervical healing. **Conclusion:** This case study shows the potential of *yoni prakshalana* and *yoni pichu* in the management of cervical erosion (*karnini yonivyapad*).

KEYWORDS: Cervical erosion, *Karnini yonivyapad*, *Yoni pichu*, *Yoni prakshalana*.

INTRODUCTION

Gynaecological disorders are a major concern for women's health due to their impact on physical, psychological, and social well-being. In Ayurveda, conditions affecting the cervix and vaginal tract are broadly classified under *Yonivyapad*. Among them, *Karnini Yonivyapad* is described with features such as abnormal vaginal discharge (*yoni srava*), itching (*yonikandu*), discomfort, and pain, attributed to vitiation of *Vata* and *Kapha dosha* along with *dushya* involvement of *Artava vaha srotas*. Local therapies like *Yoni prakshalana* (herbal decoction douche) and *Yoni pichu* (intravaginal tampon therapy with medicated oils) are advocated for cleansing, healing, and restoring the integrity of cervical and vaginal mucosa. Classical formulations such as *Nimbaadi kwatha*—renowned for its *krimighna*, *kandughna* and *shothahara* (anti-infective, anti-pruritic, and anti-inflammatory) properties—and *Jatyadi taila*-indicated for *vrana ropana* (wound healing)- play a significant role in local management.

From the modern standpoint, cervical erosion, also referred to as cervical ectopy, represents the extension of columnar epithelium onto the ectocervix. It frequently manifests with persistent Leucorrhoea, vaginal irritation, and sometimes post-coital bleeding, although asymptomatic cases are also common.^[3] Chronic cervicitis, microbial infections, hormonal influences, and mechanical irritation are recognized etiological factors. While standard treatment modalities include cauterization, cryotherapy, electrosurgery, and antimicrobial therapy, these procedures may be invasive, associated with recurrence, or raise concerns in unmarried or nulliparous women.^[4]

Given these limitations, integrative approaches using Ayurvedic modalities provide a promising, minimally invasive, and cost-effective alternative. By combining the antimicrobial and tissue-healing potential of Ayurvedic formulations with the diagnostic precision of modern gynecology, patient-centered care can be enhanced. This case report presents the

management of cervical erosion in an unmarried young female using *Yoni prakshalana* with *Nimbaadi kwatha* and *Yoni pichu* with *Jatyadi taila*, offering insights into the potential role of Ayurveda in cervical health.

CASE REPORT

A 22-year-old unmarried female reported to the *Prasuti Tantra* and *Stree Roga* OPD on 25/08/2025 with complaints of persistent white discharge per vaginally for the last six months with vaginal itching and local discomfort. She had previously received allopathic treatment but did not achieve satisfactory relief. She denied any history of sexual exposure, systemic illness, or recent drug intake. Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for participation in the study and for publication at this case report.

Menstrual History

Age of Menarche – 13 years

LMP – 05/09/2025

Pattern – Regular

Clots – Absent

Flow – Moderate

Duration – 2 - 3 days

Pad – 3-4 pads/day

Cycle Interval – 30-34 days

Pain – Mild

Colour – Dark Red

Foul smell – Absent

Marital History: Unmarried

Personal History

Diet – Mixed

Sleep – Normal

Appetite – Normal

Bowel Habit – 1-2 times/day

Micturition – Clear

Urine Frequency – 5-6 times per day

Allergic History – Nil

Addiction – Tea (2 times/day)

Examinations

Table 1: Physical Examination.

G.C.	Fair
Built	Moderate
Weight	42 Kg
Height	5'2''
BP	110/80 mmHg
Pulse Rate	74/min
Pallor	Absent

Systemic Examinations

CNS – Conscious, well oriented

CVS – S₁S₂ heard, no murmur

R/S – AEBE clear

Local Examination

P/A – Soft, Mild lower abdominal pain present

P/S – Cervix- erosion++ on both lips

Cervix – 85% of cervix

Type of Discharge - Thick milky white discharge

P/V – Uterus is anteverted, anteflexed normal size mobile

Fornix – Clear

Cervical motion tenderness – + ve on bimanual examination

Investigations

CBC – Hb% - 11.6gm%,

WBC - 8500/cu.mm

HIV – non-reactive

HbsAg – non-reactive

RBS – 98 mg/dl

Urine Routine – Albumin- Nil,

Sugar - Nil

Urine Microscopy – Pus cells - 6-7 cells,

Epi. Cells - 3-4 cells

Diagnosis

Karnini yonivyapad (Cervical erosion)

THERAPEUTIC INTERVENTION

Internal Medicine

<i>Pushyanug churna</i>	3 gm Bd after meal	With <i>Tandulodak</i>
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Local Procedures

1. *Yoni Prakshalana*

Drug used: *Nimbaadi Kwatha* (prepared fresh daily as per classical reference).

Procedure: The decoction was prepared by boiling the coarse powder in water, reduced to one-fourth, filtered, and cooled to lukewarm temperature. *Yoni prakshalana* was administered once daily in lithotomy position under aseptic precautions.

Duration: 7 consecutive days.

12. *Yoni Pichu*

Drug used: *Jatyadi Taila*.

Procedure: Sterile gauze pieces (*pichu*) were soaked in medicated oil and placed over the cervix for 4 hours after the *prakshalana* procedure.

Duration: 7 consecutive days.

Advice

- Maintain proper genital hygiene.
- Avoid tight or synthetic clothing, use cotton undergarments and change them daily.
- Avoid use of chemical based intimate washes.
- Avoid coitus during infection.

OBSERVATIONAL PARAMETERS

Subjective parameters: Vaginal discharge (quantity, colour, consistency), itching, local discomfort.

Objective parameters: Condition of cervical mucosa (congestion, erosion size), presence of discharge on per speculum examination.

Assessment

Table 2: Findings.

DAYS	FINDINGS
0 th day	White discharge, vaginal itching, cervical erosion, local discomfort.
3 rd day	White discharge reduced to 40%, vaginal itching reduced to 70%, cervical erosion healed by 30%, local discomfort reduced 50%
5 th day	White discharge reduced to 80%, vaginal itching 100% relieved, cervical erosion healed by 60%, local discomfort 80%
7 th day	White discharge reduced to 99%, cervical erosion healed by 90%, local discomfort 100% relieved

Fig. 1: Before treatment.

Fig. 2: During treatment.

Fig. 3: After treatment. (7th day)

Fig. 4: After 15 days.

After 15 days: Cervical erosion healed by 90 %, White Discharge reduced to 99%.

P/S cervix: Cervix Healthy.

RESULTS

After seven consecutive days of treatment with *Yoni prakshalana* using *Nimbaadi Kwatha* followed by *Yoni pichu* with *Jatyadi taila*, the patient reported a marked reduction in

symptoms and got relieved. The intensity of vaginal discharge decreased significantly from profuse to minimal, with improvement in consistency. Associated complaints of itching and local discomfort subsided almost completely by the end of the therapy.

On per speculum examination, after 7 days, the cervix appeared healthier with visible reduction in congestion and healing of the eroded area. No adverse effects such as local irritation, burning, or pain were noted during or after the procedures. The overall clinical response was assessed as satisfactory, indicating effective management of cervical erosion through local Ayurvedic measures.

Follow up - On per speculum examination conducted after 15 days of follow up the cervix appeared healthier with marked healing of the eroded area and reduction in local congestion. The patient has no further complaints and reported complete relief.

DISCUSSION

Cervical erosion is a frequently encountered gynaecological condition, particularly among young women, which often present with persistent leucorrhoea and local discomfort.

From the Ayurvedic perspective, this condition can be correlated to *Karnini Yonivyapad*, where vitiated *Kapha* causes excessive discharge and itching, while *Vata* leads to pain and local discomfort. The treatment principle involves *shodhana* (cleansing) and *ropana* (healing) of the local tissues.

Nimbaadi Kwatha has *krimighna* (antimicrobial), *kandughna* (anti-pruritic), and *shothahara* (anti-inflammatory) properties. Its vaginal douche action helps cleanse secretions, reduces microbial growth, and soothes inflamed mucosa.^[5]

Jatyadi Taila is well-documented for *vrana ropana* (wound healing) due to its herbal constituents like *Jati*, *Nimba*, *Patola*, and *Haridra*. Local application through *Yoni pichu* provides sustained contact with the cervix, promoting epithelial regeneration and reducing erosion.^[6]

The outcome in this case demonstrates that local Ayurvedic interventions can effectively alleviate symptoms and promote mucosal healing without invasive procedures. These therapies offer a safe, cost-effective, and patient-friendly alternative, especially for young and unmarried women where surgical interventions may not be suitable.^[7]

CONCLUSION

This case highlights the successful management of cervical erosion (*Karnini Yonivyapad*) using *Yoni prakshalana* with *Nimbaadi kwatha* and *Yoni pichu* with *Jatyadi taila* for seven days. The therapy effectively reduced vaginal discharge, itching, and local discomfort while promoting cervical healing. Ayurvedic local measures can serve as safe, non-invasive, and holistic alternatives for managing cervical erosion, warranting further clinical evaluation through large-scale studies.

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